

KRILL MORPHOLOGICAL DIFFERENTIATION. BODY PROPORTIONS IN EUPHAUSIIDS OF THE EASTERN TROPICAL NORTH PACIFIC, CALIFORNIA CURRENT AND ANTARCTIC SPECIES

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Euphausiids samples obtained in different areas, were analyzed to understand the possible differences on development patterns, and sexual morphological differentiation. *Euphausia superba*, *Euphausia pacifica*, *Euphausia distinguenda* and *Euphausia diomedea*, from the *Euphausia* genus, and *Thysanoessa spinifera*, *Thysanoessa macrura*, from the *Thysanoessa* genus, and *Nyctiphanes simplex*. Here we analyze the body proportions for each species, using four different measurements and the Differentiation Index. Simple regressions were obtained, and they showed a different pattern of morphological differentiation, for each genus. Following that evidence, multivariate analyses were performed, confirming these findings. A new concept is here proposed, the mean Differentiation Index difference between males and females, here called ΔDI , for each species, was obtained, mean values for the species obtained in each area was related to the mean temperature and the mean sigma T values, obtained for the first 400 m layer in each area. For the Sigma T values, they follow the same trend as the ΔDI , and opposed to temperature.

Antarctic *E. superba* showed the greatest differences between males and females, and especially between Males II and females. For the *Thysanoessa* genus the trend followed a different pattern. Other factors may influence these differences; probably higher lipids contents which helps in buoyancy, and different sexual reproduction seasons of the different genera may produce other development patterns in the *Thysanoessa* genus, as for the *Nyctiphanes* genus we do not have a possible comparison with another species from the same genus.